

How Motivation, Competency, and Working Environment Affect Employee Performance in Indonesian Private University

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study to determine: 1) Motivation, Competence, Work Environment and Performance of Employees in Private-owned Politechnic; 2) to determine the effect of motivation on Employee Performance, 3) to determine the effect of Competence on employee performance; 4) to determine the effect of Work Environment Employee Performance; 5) to determine the effect of Motivation, Competence and the Work Environment simultaneously on Employee Performance Politeknik Swasta. The method is a method of research used census (population) of 35 respondents using descriptive analysis and verifikatif.

From the results of descriptive analysis showed that the total effect of motivation (X1) of the Employee Performance (Y) of 63.3%, the total effect of Competency (X2) of the Employee Performance (Y) of 14.8%, and the total effect of Work Environment (X3) Performance of Employees (Y) of 7.7%. While the influence of Competence, Motivation, Corporate Culture of Performance jointly or simultaneously have the effect of a total of 85.8%.

KEYWORD: Motivation, Competence, Work Environment and Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

The organization is a forum that shows the division of tasks between people in the organization to achieve the desired goals by being mutually correlated, interdependent and integrated in achieving the effectiveness of the institution's work. Human resources (HR) are the most important resources owned by an organization, in other words that human resources can make other resources of an organization.

The Private University, located in Bandung, Indonesia, currently has 35 employees to manage 4 work areas: academic, general administration and finance, student affairs, cooperation and marketing. With a total number of students being handled reaching 300 people for 2 batches in one period, in terms of quality with the workload that must be done, the number of employees is still lacking, especially for employees who have the required qualifications.

The demand to provide excellent service to every academic community (students) requires the availability of human resources who have excellent competence, but the enrichment (development) of competence by providing training to every human resource is observed to be very minimal at all by this Private University in Bandung. Likewise, career development and achievement are rarely planned systematically, so they often only develop randomly and consequently career development and achievement often do not place human resources according to their abilities. Finally, the goals of institutions and individuals are difficult or even impossible to achieve.

In addition, there is no work attitude that indicates an internal urge for most employees to come to power, but this is generally based on the existence of a family system that is still thick in the organization at this Private University so that this phenomenon exists, even though they crave a role and a high position and want to be appreciated, both in his work environment and in the midst of society in general.

In addition, internally, the problem faced is that the attendance rate of the employees of the Private University located in Bandung, Indonesia, is quite low, as well as the delay rate is quite high which the authors assume their level of motivation towards the work of employees at one of the Private Universitys located in Bandung is quite low. .

In addition, most of the recruitment (recruitment) of employees at one of the private universitys located in Bandung is not linear with the field of work, so many intellectual education but not in accordance with work competencies. This data shows that competence in terms of knowledge is very low.

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From Field Observations, the seriousness of this Private University employee in improving performance is felt to be relatively not optimal because the work environment has not provided comfort to its employees. The indication can be seen from the work environment that can support the implementation of the work is a physical work environment such as office infrastructure. The arrangement of office infrastructure in supporting office administration at the Private University in Bandung is still lacking, the condition of the work space at the Private University in Bandung, especially the academic section, is inadequate with the number of employees occupying the room because the number of employees occupying the room exceeds capacity so that it often causes noise. This shows that the performance is not optimal when viewed in terms of the work environment in this Private University located in Bandung.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Motivation

There are many definitions given by the authors about motivation. (McShane and Von Glinow in Wibowo, 2014), provide a definition of motivation as a force within a person that influences direction, intensity, and persistence towards a particular goal (direction). Motivation is one of the four important drivers of individual behavior and performance.

Work motivation is the result of a collection of internal and external forces that cause workers to choose the appropriate course of action and adopt certain behaviors. Ideally, this behavior will be directed at achieving organizational goals (Newstrom in Wibowo, 2014). Meanwhile Newstrom suggests that as an indicator of motivation are:

1. Engagement. Engagement is an employee's promise to show a level of enthusiasm, initiative, and effort to continue.
2. Commitment. Commitment is the degree to which employees bind to the organization and demonstrate organizational citizenship actions.
3. Satisfaction. Satisfaction is a reflection of fulfilling psychological contracts and meeting expectations at work.
4. Turnover. Turnover is the loss of a valued worker.

From the opinions above, it can be concluded that motivation is an urge to act on a series of processes of human behavior by considering the direction, intensity, and persistence in achieving goals. While the elements contained in motivation include elements of generating, directing, maintaining, showing intensity, being continuous and having a purpose. (Wibowo, 2014).

Competence

There are many definitions or definitions of competence from various experts, including According to Lyle Spencer & Signe Spencer (Sudarmanto, 2014), competence is a basic characteristic of individual behavior related to effective reference criteria and or superior performance in work or situations.

According to Michael Armstrong (Sudarmanto, 2014), competence is what people bring to a job in the form of different types and levels of behavior. Competence determines the process aspects of job performance.

The State Civil Service Agency (Sudarmanto, 2014: 49), defines competence as the abilities and characteristics possessed by a Civil Servant in the form of knowledge, skills, and behavioral attitudes needed in carrying out their duties, so that the Civil Servant can carry out their duties professionally, effective, and efficient.

It can be concluded from the understanding of the experts above regarding the definition of competence is the ability that a person has in carrying out actions, work, and characteristics that exist in him in achieving certain improvements.

Work Environment

Human life is inseparable from the various circumstances of the surrounding environment, between humans and the environment there is a very close relationship. In this case, humans will always try to adapt to various environmental conditions around them. Likewise, when doing work, employees as humans cannot be separated from the various circumstances around where they work, namely the work environment. While doing work, each employee will interact with various conditions in the work environment

According to Mangkunegara (2005) states that the work environment is all aspects of physical work, work psychology and work regulations that can affect job satisfaction and productivity achievement.

Meanwhile, according to Sedarmayanti (2001) states that the work environment is the whole of tools and materials faced by the surrounding environment in which a person works, work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as groups.

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Meanwhile, according to Nitisemito (2000), the work environment is everything that is around the workers that can affect him in carrying out the tasks assigned.

The role of a good work environment is as a motivator for employees so that they feel comfortable in doing their jobs, can be more enthusiastic, and in the end can work optimally, so it cannot be denied that the work environment in a company gets further attention than at times. previous time. This can happen because as a person's standard of living increases, he will tend to want an atmosphere that provides support in carrying out his work.

Performance

In various literatures, the notion of performance is very diverse. Performance refers to understanding as a result. In the context of results, Bernardin (Sudarmanto, 2014) states that performance is a record of the results produced (generated) on certain job functions or activities over a certain period of time. From this definition, Bernardin emphasizes the notion of performance as a result, not character traits (traits) and behavior. Understanding performance as an outcome is also related to productivity and effectiveness (Ricard in Sudarmanto, 2014). Productivity is the relationship between the number of goods and services produced and the amount of labor, capital, and resources used in that production (Miner in Sudarmanto, 2014).

While performance refers to understanding as behavior. Related to performance as behavior, (Ricard in Sudarmanto, 2014) states that performance is a set of behaviors that are relevant to the goals of the organization or organizational unit where people work.

There is no standard minimum or maximum number for a single job. Having multiple standards helps employees understand more clearly what is expected and also helps managers pinpoint specific strengths and areas for improvement. Managers and workers must determine the number of suitable and practical performance standards so that their implementation is effective (Wibowo, 2014).

John Miner in Sudarmanto (2014), suggests 4 dimensions that can be used as benchmarks in assessing performance, namely:

- a. Quality, namely; error rate, damage, accuracy.
- b. Quantity, namely; the number of jobs produced.
- c. The use of time in work, namely; absenteeism, tardiness, effective working time / lost working hours.
- d. Collaborate with others at work.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses descriptive analysis method. Descriptive method is a method in examining the status of a human group of an object, a set of conditions, a system of thought or a class of events in the present. The purpose of this descriptive research is to make a systematic, factual and accurate description, picture or painting of the facts and the relationship between the phenomena being investigated. Descriptive analysis method is used to test hypotheses or answer research questions.

The use of analytical descriptive method in this study, is to get an overview of the Motivation, Competence, and Work Environment on Employee Performance at Private Universitys.

To collect data to be processed and analyzed, we need to determine the population first. The definition of population according to Sugiyono (2011) is as follows: "Population is a generalization area consisting of: objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions. While the sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. Based on the research above, the population and sample in this study were all 35 employees at Private Universitys.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of processing the data, it is obtained that the Motivation Picture (X1) is with an average score of 3.65. The average score is in accordance with the table of interpretation criteria, including the Good category. The available work facilities help me in completing my work (4,29); I have the initiative in working to improve performance (4,23).

However, there are still weak aspects, namely: I always look for information in my work to improve the quality of work (3.06); The salary/wages I receive every month can motivate me to work better (2.77).

According to the results of data processing, a Competency Picture (X2) was obtained, with an average score of 3.20. The average score is in accordance with the table of interpretation criteria, including the category of Fairly Good. The description of motivation is said to be quite good, among others because I always read library books related to my assignments (3,71); I always greet employees and management first in a friendly and polite manner (3,71).

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However, there are still weak aspects, including: I understand the scope of my work duties (2.71); The trainings provided by the institution really support the skills I need (2,37).

The results of data processing on the Work Environment (X3) with an average score of 3.11. The average score is in accordance with the table of interpretation criteria, including the category of Fairly Good. The statement is declared Good Enough because the lighting arrangement is very good, so it does not interfere with work activities (3.77); The white paint color on the walls of the workspace makes me feel comfortable (3,77).

However, there are still weak aspects, including: Ventilation arrangements in the company make work smooth and not humid (2,34); Noise can interfere with comfort at work (2,26).

Based on the results of data processing, it can be obtained a picture of Performance (Y) with an average score of 3.50. The average score is in accordance with the table of interpretation criteria, including the Good category. The performance at this Private University is said to be good because in achieving the results according to the target, I still avoid waste (4.06); The results that I complete are always in accordance with the targets that have been set by the leadership (3.91).

However, there are still some weak aspects, including: I always carry out the overtime assigned by my superior if the work must be completed immediately (3.00); I always carry out my duties in accordance with applicable work procedures so that the results obtained are in accordance with the established standards (2.89).

In accordance with the results of data processing carried out, the results of the Influence of Motivation (X1) on Performance (Y) are direct effect of 0.482 or 48.2%, indirect effect through Competence (X2) of 0.96 or 9.6%, indirectly through the Work Environment (X3) by 0.055% or 5.5%. Thus the total effect is 0.633 or 63.3%. Where this motivation variable has the greatest total influence value compared to other variables.

The results of data processing indicate that there is an influence of motivation on employee performance. Thus, the hypothesis proposed in this study is proven, namely that there is a significant effect of motivation on employee performance

In accordance with the results of data processing carried out, the results of the Effect of Competence (X2) on Performance (Y) are a direct effect of 0.039 or 3.9%, an indirect effect through motivation (X1) of 0.096 or 9.6%, an indirect effect through the Work Environment (X3) by 0.013 or 1.3%. Thus the total effect is 0.148 or 14.8%.

The results of data processing indicate that there is an influence of competence on employee performance. Thus, the hypothesis proposed in this study is proven, namely that there is a significant effect of Competence on Employee Performance.

In accordance with the results of data processing carried out, the results obtained are the Effect of the Work Environment (X3) on Performance (Y), namely the direct effect of 0.009 or 0.9%, the indirect effect through Motivation (X1) of 0.054 or 5.4%, the indirect effect of directly through Competence (X2) of 0.013 or 1.3%. Thus the total effect is 0.077 or 7.7%.

The results of data processing indicate that there is an influence of the Work Environment on performance. Thus, the hypothesis proposed in this study is proven, namely that there is a significant effect of the Work Environment on Employee Performance

In accordance with the results of data processing carried out, the results obtained that the Effect of Motivation (X1), Competence (X2), and Work Environment (X3) on Employee Performance (Y) together or simultaneously have a total effect of 0.858 or 85.8% . These results indicate that the influence of the three variables is included in the significant category.

This is also in accordance with several previous studies which prove that the variables of Motivation, Competence and Work Environment, together increase Employee Performance.

This shows that the three variables mentioned above, namely Motivation (X1), Competence (X2), and Work Environment together and in good synergy have a significant influence on Employee Performance at Private Universitys.

The remaining 0.142 or 14.2% are other variables not examined, including internal communication, cooperation between employees, education and training, awards for achievement, employee placement, compensation, facilities and infrastructure, work climate, organizational culture and others.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data processing and discussion of Work Motivation, Competence and Work Environment on Employee Performance at Private Universitys in Bandung, the authors conclude as follows:

1. Description of Motivation (X1) with an average score of 3.65. The average score is in accordance with the table of interpretation criteria, including the Good category. The available work facilities help me in completing my work (4,29); I have the initiative in working to improve performance (4,23). However, there are still weak aspects, namely: I always look

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for information in my work to improve the quality of work (3.06); The salary/wages I receive every month can motivate me to work better (2.77).

2. Description of Competence (X2) with an average score of 3.20. The average score is in accordance with the table of interpretation criteria, including the category of Fairly Good. The description of motivation is said to be quite good, among others because I always read library books related to my assignments (3,71); I always greet employees and management first in a friendly and polite manner (3,71). However, there are still weak aspects, including: I understand the scope of my work duties (2.71); The trainings provided by the institution really support the skills I need (2,37).
3. Description of the Work Environment (X3) with an average score of 3.11. The average score is in accordance with the table of interpretation criteria, including the category of Fairly Good. The statement is declared Good Enough because the lighting arrangement is very good, so it does not interfere with work activities (3.77); The white paint color on the walls of the workspace makes me feel comfortable (3,77). However, there are still weak aspects, including: Ventilation arrangements in the company make work smooth and not humid (2,34); Noise can interfere with comfort at work (2,26).
4. Performance Description (Y) with an average score of 3.50. The average score is in accordance with the table of interpretation criteria, including the Good category. The performance at this Private University is said to be good because in achieving the results according to the target, I still avoid waste (4.06); The results that I complete are always in accordance with the targets that have been set by the leadership (3.91). However, there are still some weak aspects, including: I always carry out the overtime assigned by my superior if the work must be completed immediately (3.00); I always carry out my duties in accordance with applicable work procedures so that the results obtained are in accordance with the established standards (2.89).
5. The influence of motivation (X1) on performance (Y) is a direct effect of 0.482 or 48.2%, an indirect effect through competence (X2) is 0.96 or 9.6%, an indirect effect is through the work environment (X3) of 0.055% or 5.5%. Thus the total effect is 0.633 or 63.3%. Where this motivation variable has the greatest total influence value compared to other variables.
6. The influence of competence (X2) on performance (Y) is a direct influence of 0.039 or 3.9%, an indirect effect through motivation (X1) of 0.096 or 9.6%, an indirect effect through the work environment (X3) of 0.013 or 1.3%. Thus the total effect is 0.148 or 14.8%.
7. The influence of the work environment (X3) on performance (Y) is a direct effect of 0.009 or 0.9%, an indirect effect through motivation (X1) is 0.054 or 5.4%, an indirect effect through competence (X2) is 0.013 or 1.3%. Thus the total effect is 0.077 or 7.7%.
8. The influence of Motivation (X1), Competence (X2), and Work Environment (X3) on Employee Performance (Y) together or simultaneously have a total effect of 0.858 or 85.8%. These results indicate that the influence of the three variables is included in the significant category.

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